

Research

Safety and Risk Likelihood Indices of Novel Coronavirus Pandemic in Nigeria

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Abstract: The adverse impact of coronavirus (covid-19) pandemic is becoming worrisome and perplexing not only to Nigerians but to the international community. This has heightened the fear; thereby threatening the foundation of economic development. This study takes a critical look on measurement of the levels of safety or risk indices of all the 20 affected state on a logarithmic scale. From computation/analysis it shows that the state with largest number of infected persons/cases has the highest risk of spread of the COVID-19. Every unit increase in the incidence Safety Index corresponds to a Risk decrease by a factor of 10. The risk and safety indices sum up to a value of 10 and their values are defined over the interval $[0, 10]$. This study presents a better understanding and awareness of likelihood safety and risk assessment for the hazardous diseases. We recommend that, the identities of the infected persons should not be hidden even for the fear of stigmatization due to the consequences associated it. The Useful insights for the allocation of resources, remedial actions, monitoring and control strategies to prevent/curtail the dynamics of (covid-19) disease spread.

Keywords: Logarithmic likelihood, safety index, risk index coronavirus (covid-19).

INTRODUCTION

Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) is an infectious disease caused by a newly discovered coronavirus. Most people infected with the COVID-19 virus will experience mild to moderate respiratory illness and recover without requiring special treatment. Older people and those with underlying medical problems like cardiovascular disease, diabetes, chronic respiratory disease, and cancer are more likely to develop serious illness. The COVID-19 virus spreads primarily

through droplets of saliva or discharge from the nose when an infected person coughs or sneezes, so it's important that you also practice respiratory etiquette (for example, by coughing into a flexed elbow). At this time, there are no specific vaccines or treatments for COVID-19. However, there are many ongoing clinical trials evaluating potential treatments. (WHO, 2020)

The world health organization gave the following basic protective measures against the novel coronavirus

Wash your hands frequently: Regularly Washing your hands with soap and water or using alcohol-based hand rub kills viruses that may be on your hands.

Maintain social distancing: Maintain at least one (1) meter (3 feet) distance between yourself and anyone who is coughing or sneezing they may spray small liquid droplets from their nose or mouth which may contain virus. If you are too close, you can breathe in the droplets, including the COVID-19 virus if the person coughing has the diseases.

Avoid touching eyes, nose and mouth: Hands touch many surfaces and can pick up viruses. Once contaminated, hands can transfer the virus to your eyes, nose or mouth. From there, the virus can enter your body and can make you sick.

Practice respiratory hygiene: Make sure you, and the people around you, follow good respiratory hygiene. This means covering your mouth and nose with your bent elbow or tissue when you cough or sneeze. Then dispose of the used tissue immediately.

If you have fever, cough and difficulty breathing, seek medical care early: Stay home if you feel unwell. If you have a fever, cough and difficulty breathing, seek medical attention and call in advance. Follow the directives of your local health authority. (WHO, 2020)

The Federal Ministry of Health through the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) has activated a national Emergency Operations Centre at the highest level and is leading the national response. National Rapid Response Teams have been deployed to support affected state governments with response activities. The NCDC is also working closely with the state governments of all affected states to carry out contact tracing. Several measures have been instituted by the Presidential Task Force on COVID-19 together with the Federal Ministry of

Health to curtail the spread of the disease and protect the health of Nigerians. In line with this, the Federal Government of Nigeria has issued a ban on all international flights effective from the 23rd of March 2020 with the exception of emergency and essential flights for an initial period of time. Directives have also been issued at national and state level, to cancel large gatherings including religious gatherings, schools, events etc. As the airports are currently shut, `Nigerians are strongly advised against non-essential inter-state travel. All travelers who have returned to Nigeria in the last 14days are required to self-isolate for 14 days even if they are not showing symptoms. The NCDC has disseminated information on the practice of self-isolation.

The Federal Government has directed the lockdown of all non-essential activities in the FCT, Lagos and Ogun States effective from the 30th of March 2020. As the Task Force continues to review response activities, more preventive measures may be instituted by the Federal and State Government in the coming days as the situation demands. (NCDC, 2020)

Keeping above in view, it should be noted that in statistics, there is a distinction between “probability” which allows the prediction of unknown outcomes based on known parameters, and “likelihood” which allows us the estimation of unknown parameters based on known outcomes. In this paper, we study Logarithmic risk and safety likelihood indices for a novel coronavirus in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Lewis [1] suggested the application of Logarithmic risk and safety incidence indices in the risk assessment for a large population that is subjected to some forms of common hazards such as disease or natural disasters. The concept for a limited size population likelihood index for the comparison of hazardous activities that are peculiar to a small population that is engaged in a hazardous or other societal activity was initiated by [2]. We can recall that logarithm to a base 10 of a number x is the power to which 10 must be raised to equal the number under consideration.

Now, let consider the following examples bellow;

$100 = 10^2$ can be written in logarithm form as $\log_{10} 100 = \log 10^2 = 2$.

$1000 = 10^3$ can be written in logarithm form as $\log_{10} 1000 = \log 10^3 = 3$.

$10000 = 10^4$ This can be written in logarithm form as $\log_{10} 10000 = \log 10^4 = 4$

In general, let the logarithm to the base 10 of x;

If $x = 10^n$,

Then $\log_{10} x = \log_{10} 10^n$

$$= n \log_{10} 10$$

$$= n \cdot 1$$

$$= n$$

Where: $\log_{10} 10^1 = 1$

$$\log_{10} 1 = \log_{10} 10^0 = 0$$

For numbers in between the powers of 10, the base 10 logarithm lies between the two nearest powers of 10. That is;

$$\log_{10} 10 = 1$$

$$\log_{10} 100 = 2$$

$$\log_{10} 500 = 2.699$$

$$\log_{10} 1000 = 3$$

$$\log_{10} 10000 = 4$$

LIKELIHOOD SAFETY INDEX

Consider a certain societal activity or exposure to natural or man-made hazards resulting in a number of infected persons, d, in a given time period such as a year. For a total population of t persons, the per capita infected person's frequency f is:

$$f_{likelihood} = \frac{d}{t} \left[\frac{\text{infected persons}}{\text{population in the state}} \right] \quad (1)$$

A logarithmic Safety Index, SI, can be defined as the logarithm to the base 10 of 1/f, or the negative logarithm to the base 10 of f as:

$$\begin{aligned} SI_{likelihood} &= \log_{10} \frac{t'}{d} = -\log_{10} \frac{d}{t'} \\ &= \log_{10} \frac{1}{f} = -\log_{10} f, \forall f \neq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The largest risky exposures correspond to lower value of Safety Index (SI). Similarly, less risky exposure corresponds to the higher value of the Safety Index (SI).

LIKELIHOOD RISK INDEX

A Risk Index RI can also be defined as follows:

$$RI_{likelihood} = 10 - SI_{likelihood} \quad (3)$$

$$= 10 - \log_{10} \frac{1}{f} = 10 + \log_{10} f, \forall f \neq 0$$

DATASETS OF THE PRACTICAL CASES

TABLE 1: SAFETY AND RISK LIKELIHOOD INDICES OF CORONAVIRUS COVID-19 PANDEMIC IN NIGERIA

STATE	POPULATION PER STATE t'	INFECTED PERSONS IN STATE d	INFECTED PERSONS RATIO $f = \frac{d}{t'}$	LIKELIHOOD SAFETY INDEX SI	LIKELIHOOD RISK INDEX RI
LAGOS	12,550,598	251	2.0×10^{-5}	4.7	5.3
ABUJA	3,564,126	67	1.9×10^{-5}	4.7	5.3
OSUN	4,705,589	20	4.3×10^{-6}	5.4	4.6
KANO	13,076,892	21	1.6×10^{-6}	5.8	4.2
EDO	4,235,595	15	3.5×10^{-6}	5.5	4.5
OYO	7,840,864	13	1.7×10^{-6}	5.8	4.2
OGUN	5,217,716	9	1.7×10^{-6}	5.8	4.2
KATSINA	7,831,319	7	8.9×10^{-7}	6.0	4.0
BAUCHI	6,537,314	6	9.2×10^{-7}	6.0	4.0
KADUNA	8,252,366	6	1.14×10^{-6}	6.1	3.9
AKWA-IBOM	5,482,177	6	2.0×10^{-6}	5.96	4.04
KWARA	3,192,893	4	1.3×10^{-6}	5.9	4.1
DELTA	5,663,362	4	7.1×10^{-7}	6.2	3.8
ONDO	4,671,695	3	6.4×10^{-7}	6.2	3.8
ENUGU	4,411,119	2	4.5×10^{-7}	6.3	3.7
EKITI	3,270,798	2	6.1×10^{-7}	6.2	3.8

RIVERS	7,303,924	2	2.7×10^{-7}	6.6	3.4
NIGER	5,556,247	2	3.6×10^{-7}	6.4	3.6
BENUE	5,741,815	1	1.7×10^{-7}	6.8	3.2
ANAMBRA	5,527,809	1	1.8×10^{-7}	6.7	3.3

SOURCE OF DATA; NATIONAL BUREAU OF STATISTICS (NBS) AND NIGERIA CENTRE FOR DISEASE CONTROL (NCDC), AS AT 10:20 PM THURSDAY 16TH APRIL 2020.

Now let determine the safety and risk likelihood indices of the two states using equation 2 and 3 as shown in table 1.

The safety and risk likelihood index of Lagos state

$$\begin{aligned}
 SI_{likelihood} &= \log_{10} \frac{t'}{d} = -\log_{10} \frac{d}{t'} \\
 &= -\log_{10} \frac{251}{12550598} \\
 &= \log_{10} \frac{12550598}{251} \\
 &= \log_{10} 50002.38247 = 4.7 \\
 RI_{likelihood} &= 10 - SI_{likelihood} \\
 &= 10 - 4.7 = 5.3
 \end{aligned}$$

The safety and risk likelihood index of Kaduna state

$$\begin{aligned}
 SI_{likelihood} &= \log_{10} \frac{t'}{d} = -\log_{10} \frac{d}{t'} \\
 &= -\log_{10} \frac{6}{8,252,366} \\
 &= \log_{10} \frac{8,252,366}{6} \\
 &= \log_{10} 1375394333 = 6.1 \\
 RI_{likelihood} &= 10 - SI_{likelihood} \\
 &= 10 - 6.1 = 3.9
 \end{aligned}$$

The graphical representation of the observation from table 1 is shown in Figures below.

FIGURE 1: POPULATION PER STATE

FIGURE 2: INFECTED PERSONS IN STATE

FIGURE 3: SAFETY and RISK LIKELIHOOD INDICES

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

We can obviously observe from table 1 that summation of safety index and risk index is 10 which is the maximum attainable value. The magnitude scale, where the larger the magnitude of the infected persons signal; the larger is the expected spread or damage from the covid-19. A value of 10 on this scale corresponds to a Safety Index of zero, or assured massive spread of disease which may lead to so many deaths. A low Risk Index corresponds to a high Safety Index, and vice versa.

From table 1 and figure 3, it is evidence that the RI of 4.0 to 5.3 for about eleven states is disturbing and scaring. These values translate to 40% - 53% of these states are at the risk of being infected with this disease. Though there is significant difference in the population between Lagos (12million) and Abuja (3million), the two cities have the same magnitude scale of 5.3 RI which is more than half of the maximum attainable value 10. The strategic influence of these states, economic and administrative headquarters respectively of the country cannot be downplayed, as all states of the federation has one activity or the other to undertake in these two states.

Also, Kano (13million), Oyo (7million) and Edo (4million) with RI of 4.2, 4.2 and 4.5 respectively implies looming fast spread of the disease as both populous states and less populated states are on the same status of the disease spread.

The two states (Benue and Anambra) with a unit infected individuals but having likelihood of infection, RI, of 3.2 and 3.3 respectively translating to 32% and 33% rate of infection, indicate the states has the lowest risk index with the magnitude scale of 3.2 and 3.3 which is less than half of the maximum attainable value 10.

The population of all the affected states, figure 1, shows a conspicuous difference from the populous states (Lagos and Kano) against the less populated states (Osun, Edo, Kwara, Abuja) but all these states, figure 3, displays rather an insignificant difference RI. This is in tandem with information when figure 2 and 3 are compared. While figure 2 shows a sharp difference in the infection numbers in these states, the RI on the other hand depicts insignificant difference in the likelihood of risk of infection.

The trajectory/trend in which the number of infected persons increases on daily basis indicates that, we are approaching a dangerous trend if precautionary steps are not taken. At this juncture, hiding the identities of the infected persons for fear of stigmatization is not the best option/practice. Assuming an infected individual associates with twenty people, there are possibilities that, the infected individual cannot give the account of all persons he associates with within that period. With good awareness strategy, the omitted persons can report to the testing center if they have known to have associated with an infected person.

Statistically, the number of recoveries/discharge persons from covid-19 worldwide and Nigerian in particular is far higher compared to the number of deaths recorded, this shows covid-19 is not a death sentence rather, a viral disease whose mortality rate increases when a person with an underlining ailment contracts it. Therefore, there is no reason to hid the identity of patients for fear of stigmatization.

However, we are expecting the number of effective contacts between infective individuals and ignorant individuals to decrease at high infective levels due to the quarantine of infective individuals and preventive measures put by the constitutional authorities in the subsequence weeks, most especially if citizens strictly follow healthcare professionals' guidelines.

The concepts of likelihood risk and safety indices can be extended where the hazard is not just deaths, but could be unemployment, injuries, economic loss, or environmental degradation. For

large ranges of variation in a different range or units for the risk estimation such as the interval [0, 100] can be used, as in Fullwood [3] who investigated such specific risk, the radiological risks where units prevail such as risk from the exposure to different effective doses of radiation. The derived likelihood safety and risk indices shown in Table 1 can be used for monitoring and implementation of control strategies of the novel virus covid-19 in Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following valuable recommendations drawn from our study.

- (i) To decrease the risk of covid-19 spread, authorities should ensure that the identities of the infected persons are not been hidden even for fear of stigmatization, consistence actions to relax public panic/fear on covid-19 cannot be overemphasized, Generally, enhancing the transparency of the information in an emergency event can achieve management aims to halting covid-19 and rumour transmission/fake news more effectively at far lower cost than traditional or political regulation.
- (ii) Excellent psychological quality provides the public with strong mental power and the ability to adhere strictly to the guidelines provided by healthcare expert, therefore psychological quality of the public has effect on the final size of covid-19 infective. To reduce covid-19 impact on society, an effective immunity against covid-19 spread through the timely publicity and popularize scientific knowledge and developing excellent psychological quality is essential.
- (iii) Government should propose efficient measures to curb the spread of the disease which will stabilize the society and protect the economy from crashing dangerously. Rumor spreading should be curbed too by updating the citizenry on the correct state of things using all the mediums adequately and generously. There should be punitive measure on rumor spreading though the social media by relevant act(s).

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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The graphic features a green globe with a plant growing from it, set against a background of green leaves and rays of light.

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